

Convert visitors into regular users

Gaining regular users implies building trust and delivering quick, reliable answers to their research needs. Here are some steps to follow:

Know your user communities

Understanding both potential and existing users is crucial for **effective onboarding**.

Gather insights through various methods such as **Matomo analytics**, **articles** and **patents** citing your resource, **helpdesk inquiries**, **course participants**, and **user surveys**.

Develop **personas** for each type of user group to ensure their research needs are met in a user-friendly manner. For guidance, refer to the [SIB UX toolkit](#) and reach out to the **Biodata Resources team** with any questions.

Ensure your website answers important questions of visitors

→ [Homepage](#)

🔗 **State the resource's value proposition**

A clear, concise, and impactful value proposition helps potential users understand why they should use your resources instead of your competitors'. Stick to what makes the resource unique and beneficial for users.

The Communications team can help you formulate such a value proposition.

🔗 **Add information about the last updates to your resource**

Showcasing regular updates of your code or data prominently builds **user trust**. For scientific **reproducibility**, providing a link to previous data versions is a good practice. See [Bgee's homepage](#) for instance.

🔗 **Include a short video tutorial**

Providing an **introductory video** tutorial helps prospective users decide whether to use your resource and explains how to **start using it quickly**. See [Cellosaurus' introductory video](#) for example.

🔗 **Display testimonials & figures**

Display testimonials from users and industry partners as well as figures on the number of citations or users. **Social proof** is important to promote adoption. Seeing evidence of widespread adoption makes leads more likely to become engaged users.

→ [«About» page](#)

When a potential user visits your website for the first time, they typically go to the «About» page to determine if your resource is trustworthy and suitable for their needs. Link to the "About" page from header and/or footer of each page and include the following elements:

- 🔗 **Description of the Resource** with lists of ontologies, data sources, etc.
- 🔗 **Release version, date, key metrics** (e.g. number of entries or species) and **change logs**.
- 🔗 **License** to use the data and/or the code.
- 🔗 **Reference paper** with a COPY button to make citation easier.
- 🔗 Terms of use and privacy policy.
- 🔗 List of Scientific Advisory Board members and/or User Advisory Board members (if applicable).
- 🔗 Staff and affiliation
- 🔗 Mention of being a **SIB Resource** (if applicable) with a link to the [related webpage](#).

The **Biodata Resources team** can help you with all this.

Don't underestimate the importance of web design and user experience

A well-designed website enhances **accessibility** for users with varying technical skills, leading to greater interaction, **increased usage**, and **higher citations**. A clear, organized site saves users' time, allowing them to focus more on their research. Moreover, a **polished, user-friendly design** elevates the **professionalism** and **credibility** of your work and institution. For guidance, refer to the [SIB UX toolkit](#) and reach out to the **Biodata Resources team** with any questions.

→ «Help» section

Providing guidance to new users is crucial for **building trust** and **encouraging engagement** with the resource. To proceed, create a landing page as on the [UniProt](#) or [STRING help centers](#). Remember, user documentation is an ongoing process that requires continuous updates and improvements based on user feedback. Add a link to the “Help” section from the header of each page.

Basically, a comprehensive user documentation should include:

🔗 An end-user documentation:

Geared toward users who are not technical and may use your resource via its web interface

🔗 A technical documentation:

Intended for a far more technical group of users – those that build or maintain data resources or services.

- 🔗 In case you run a database or software as a service: available formats, API and SPARQL endpoint documentation and example queries.
- 🔗 In case you have developed a standalone version of your resource, it is convenient to provide your user community with a 1-page cheat sheet on how to use the resource. See for example “[OMA standalone cheat sheet](#)”
- 🔗 In case you provide a software tool or pipeline: how to install, configure, benchmark. See [V-pipe's help page](#).

🔗 Frequently asked questions:

FAQs collect recurring questions from the **helpdesk**. See the [UniProt's FAQs](#) for example.

🔗 Tutorials and training materials:

Provide tutorials so that new users have a handy **step-by-step guide** to refer to (see the [ASAP tutorials](#) for example).

You can also contact the [SIB Training group](#) who can organize a course (videos and materials will be made public) or work with you to create an e-learning course (see the [Cellosaurus e-learning course](#) for example).

→ «Contact» page

A contact page helps convey that your resource is backed by a **real and solid organization**. To achieve this, include an email address or a contact form, ensuring it is easily accessible from both the header and footer of each page. Respond promptly to inquiries and use the user feedback to **enhance your FAQs** and **prioritize new developments for your resource**.

→ Footer

Display **badges of recognition, logos** and **funders** to reinforce the perception of **trustworthiness**. Ensure the **SIB logo is displayed**, accompanied by the tagline: “[Your resource name] is part of [SIB's portfolio of open databases and software tools](#)” (be sure to include the link). Additionally, incorporate mentions such as (but not limited to):

- 🔗 **ELIXIR-CH Service Delivery Plan, Core Data Resources, Recommended Interoperability Resources, or Deposition databases, Global Core Biodata Resources** (if applicable)
- 🔗 **Community or quality labels** (e.g. IRDiRC, CoreTrustSeal, etc.)
- 🔗 List **funders** to strengthen the perception of **sustainability**.

Your contacts:

[Communications team](#)
[Biodata Resources team](#)

Swiss Institute of
Bioinformatics